

Preparation and Reactivity of Phenylmercury Trichloroacetate

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Phenylmercury trichloroacetate and its molecular adducts with several Lewis bases have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, molar conductance, ir and pmr spectroscopic data. The presence of unidentate trichloroacetate group is concluded.

PHENYLMERCURY trichloroacetate is reported to have been prepared^{1,2} but its reactivity has not been examined. In this communication we report the preparation of the compound in better yield by a different method using direct mercuriation of benzene. Its interaction with Lewis bases (L) such as 4-picoline (4-pic), tetramethylpiperidine (TMP), tetramethylethylenediamine (TMEN), ethylenediamine (en), pyridine N-oxide (PyO), 4-picoline N-oxide (4-PicO), N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF), triphenylphosphine (TPP), thiourea (TU) and diphenylthiourea (DPTU) resulted in the formation of the adducts $\text{PhHgOCOCCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}$. Reaction with 3-picoline N-oxide (3-PicO), lutidine N-oxide (LutO) and triphenylphosphine sulphide (TPPS) gave the products $\text{PhHgCCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}'$ ($\text{L}' = 3\text{-PicO}$, LutO or TPPS). The reaction of tetraalkyl ammonium halides R_4NX ($\text{R} = \text{Me}$, Et; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br), resulted in the formation of ionic products $[\text{R}_4\text{N}]_2^+ \cdot [\text{PhHgClX}_2]^{2-}$.

Experimental

Trichloroacetic acid (B.D.H.) was recrystallised before use. The Lewis bases were obtained from Alpha Inorganics and Aldrich Chemicals, U.S.A. The liquid bases were distilled and solid bases were recrystallised from suitable solvents before use. Solvents were dried by conventional methods. All operations were carried out under dry nitrogen using conventional ground glass apparatus. Physico-chemical studies were made as described earlier³.

Phenylmercury trichloroacetate was prepared by direct mercuriation of benzene using yellow mercuric oxide and trichloroacetic acid. In a typical experiment a mixture of yellow HgO (20 mmole) and CCl_3COOH (20 mmole) in dry benzene (40 ml) was heated at 60-70° for ~4 hr and filtered hot. The filtrate was distilled under reduced pressure to remove excess of the solvent. The concentrate on keeping in a deep freeze yielded the desired product as a white crystalline solid. It was recrystallized from dichloromethane, m.p. 238°(d), yield 92%. (Found : Hg, 45.26. Calcd. ; Hg, 45.59%).

Preparation of the adducts: The molecular adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis bases with phenylmercury trichloroacetate.

In a representative experiment, to a solution of TU (5 mmole) in dichloromethane (~20 ml) was added a solution of phenylmercury trichloroacetate (5 mmole) in the same solvent (~20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for ~4 hr. The product was placed in a deep freeze. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from acetone or dichloromethane. In several cases where the product did not separate on cooling, the adduct was precipitated by the addition of excess pet. ether (60-80°). It was washed with the same solvent and recrystallised from acetone or dichloromethane.

The experimental data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data correspond to 1 : 1 (metal base) stoichiometry. The adducts are thermally stable and unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are sharp melting solids, white to light brown in colour and are generally soluble in common organic solvents. The molar conductance of the adducts ($10^{-3}M$) in nitrobenzene suggests their non-ionic nature. The molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in freezing nitrobenzene. The values (Table 1) show their monomeric nature.

IR spectra: The ir spectra of the adducts were recorded in KBr in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} and absorptions of diagnostic values are discussed.

The assignments for absorptions due to carboxyl group were made on the basis of the reported spectrum of sodium trichloroacetate⁴. Trichloroacetate group can bind to the metal atom either as monodentate or bidentate, or in the ionic form. The value of $\Delta\nu\text{OCO}$ ($\nu_{\text{asymOCO}} - \nu_{\text{symOCO}}$) has been utilized for the determination of the nature of bonding between the carboxylate group and the metal atom^{5,6}. For unidentate bonding the value is the highest⁷ and lies around 350 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of phenylmercury trichloroacetate and its molecular adducts the separation value ($\Delta\nu\text{OCO}$)

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION DATA FOR $\text{PhHgOCOCCL}_3 \cdot \text{L}$

L	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd)		Mol. weight Found (Calcd.)	IR absorption in cm^{-1}		
			Hg	Cl		$\nu_{\text{as}}\text{OCO}$	$\nu_{\text{s}}\text{OCO}$	$\Delta\nu\text{OCO}$
4-Pic	118 d	78	37.43 (37.64)	19.78 (20.00)	518 (533)	1678	1336	342
TMP	172	81	34.28 (34.51)	18.13 (18.33)	563 (581)	1668	1325	343
TMEN	174	64	35.91 (36.08)	19.06 (19.15)	530 (556)	1670	1325	345
en	178	66	34.46 (40.12)	21.13 (21.30)	488 (500)	1675	1320	355
PyO	102 d	64	37.19 (37.49)	19.73 (19.90)	511 (535)	1680	1330	350
4-PicO	166	89	36.38 (36.54)	19.18 (19.39)	527 (549)	1680	1328	352
DMF	208 d	72	38.88 (39.10)	20.52 (20.75)	503 (513)	1672	1328	344
TPP	89	82	28.31 (28.57)	15.01 (15.17)	678 (702)	1682	1336	346
TU	122 d	91	38.61 (38.87)	20.43 (20.64)	497 (516)	1675	1330	345
DPTU	119 d	79	30.29 (30.48)	16.03 (16.18)	631 (658)	1668	1310	358

lies at $350 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which distinctly indicates the unidentate character of the carboxylato group. The low value of conductance in nitrobenzene further supports this conclusion.

The characteristic absorptions supporting the presence of coordinated bases are given below.

N-donors (4-pic, TMP, TMEN, en): The $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ appearing at $1584, 1240$ and 1253 cm^{-1} in 4-pic⁹, TMP⁹ and TMEN⁹, respectively shifts to $1620, 1225$ and 1295 cm^{-1} in the corresponding adducts, indicating Hg←N coordination. The shift of $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ from 3375 in free en¹⁰ to 3100 cm^{-1} in the adduct suggests the presence of the coordinated base.

O-donors (PyO, 4-PicO, DMF): The strong band at $1258 \pm 7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$ in the free PyO and 4-picO suffers a significant negative shift and appears at $1225 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the adducts suggesting Hg←O coordination¹¹. The absorption due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ in free DMF¹² appearing at 1670 cm^{-1} shifts to 1620 cm^{-1} in the adduct indicating coordination through the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group.

P-donor (TPP): Triphenyl phosphine coordinates through its P atom which is evident from the positive shift of $\nu\text{P}-\text{C}$ vibrational mode from 1089 cm^{-1} in the free base to 1105 cm^{-1} in the adduct¹³.

S-donors (TU and DPTU): The $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ appearing at 1417 and 760 cm^{-1} in free TU¹⁴ and DPTU¹⁵, respectively shifts to 1400 and 740 cm^{-1} in the corresponding adducts indicating coordination through the S atom of the bases.

¹H NMR spectra: The ¹H nmr spectrum of the adduct, $\text{PhHgOCOCCL}_3 \cdot \text{TMP}$ shows a singlet centered at 7.26 ppm due to the phenyl protons attached to the Hg atom. The singlet centered at 6.5 ppm corresponds to NH proton of TMP. The singlets at 1.57 and 1.38 ppm are attributed to CH_2 and CH_3 protons, respectively. The spectra and

their integrations are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the adduct.

On the basis of analytical, ir and ¹H nmr data it is suggested that PhHgOCOCCL_3 has a diagonal structure containing a two coordinate Hg atom. In the molecular adducts of 1 : 1 (metal:base) stoichiometry the Hg atom is involved in planar three coordination with unidentate bases while a tetrahedral coordination may be assigned with bidentate bases. A limited number of three coordinate Hg(II) complexes have so far been reported^{16,17}.

It was observed that 3-picO, LutO and TPPS (Ph_3PS) on reaction with PhHgOCOCCL_3 gave products which analysed correctly to the formula $\text{PhHgCCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}$ (L = 3-picO, LutO, TPPS). The ir spectra show the absence of absorptions due to OCO stretching and the presence of absorptions due to C—Cl stretching significantly shifted downward from 840 cm^{-1} in PhHgOCOCCL_3 to $800-810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the products. Such type of interactions have not been described earlier but $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2 \cdot \text{bipy}$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2 \cdot \text{phen}$ are reported¹⁸ to lose CO_2 at their m.p.s giving rise to the products of the formulae $\text{Hg}(\text{CF}_3)_2 \cdot \text{bipy}$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{CF}_3)_2 \cdot \text{phen}$, respectively. The course of such reactions have also been studied by ir spectra¹⁸.

Interaction of PhHgOCOCCL_3 with R_4NX (R = Me, Et and X = Cl, Br) has yielded a product of the formula $[\text{R}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{PhHgCl}_2]$. IR spectra show the absence of absorptions due to OCO and C—Cl stretchings.

Antimicrobial activity of phenylmercury trichloroacetate and its adducts was evaluated against five bacteria (*Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and five fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporotrichum schenckii*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Asper-*

gillus fumigatus) by two fold serial dilution technique¹⁹.

Most of the compounds are active only against *Streptococcus faecalis* and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. The results show that the activity of the parent compound is not enhanced on adduct formation.

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